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Доцент кафедры философии и логики**СОЗДАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ БИБЛИОТЕК ДЛЯ СЛЕПЫХ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ КАК
ФАКТОР ИХ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ****АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье анализируется история создания специальных библиотек, которые считаются одним из важных факторов в процессе социализации людей с ограниченными возможностями по зрению. При этом анализируется процесс появления специальных библиотек в Узбекистане и тенденции развития в новейшее время. Также уделяется внимание категории культурной компетентности, которая является важным элементом концепции социализации.

Ключевые слова. Инвалиды по зрению, специальные библиотеки, социализация, шрифт Брайля, мобильная библиотека, аудиоклубы, Общество слепых Узбекистана, Марокканский контракт, специальное издательство.

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ORGANIZATION OF BLIND LIBRARIES IN UZBEKISTAN AS A FACTOR OF THEIR SOCIALIZATION

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the history of the establishment of special libraries, which are considered one of the important factors in the process of socialization of people with visual disabilities. In this, the process of the emergence of special libraries in Uzbekistan and the development trends in modern times are analyzed. Attention is also paid to the category of cultural competence, which is an important element of the concept of socialization.

Key words: visually impaired people, special libraries, socialization, braille, mobile library, audio clubs, blind society of Uzbekistan, Treaty of Morocco, special publishing house.

Introduction. A significant amount of research in the field of pedagogy, general and developmental psychology, sociology, social philosophy is devoted to the problem of socialization (T. Parsons, A. Lorenzer, J. Mead, L. S. Vygodsky, A. N. Leontiev and others). In the most general terms, socialization is understood as "... the process of personality formation, the assimilation of social experience, during which the most general, stable personality traits are formed" (E. P. Polikanova). Based on the work of researchers in the phenomenology of socialization, we can conclude that this is a multi-stage and multi-factor process of individual development and adaptation to the world around us. This process, first of all, includes the individual's assimilation of the cultural environment and cultural values and traditions of society, laws and norms of social behavior and their observance.

Literature Review. Analysis of the literature shows that socialization is the most important factor in the formation of personality in society. In this article, T. Parsons, A. Lawrancer, Dj. Mead, L. S. Vygodsky, A. N. Leontev, T. Y. Kuznetsova, based on the researches, the ontological existence of socialization and the forming factors of this social phenomenon were considered. At the same time, factors of socialization of visually impaired persons were considered based on the factor of special libraries in Uzbekistan.

These are the texts of international documents:

The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by the UN on December 12, 2006 [1]

The Law "On the Rights of the Disabled" adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 22, 2020; [2]

"Treaty of Morocco" adopted in Morocco on June 27, 2013 and entered into force on September 30, 2016. [3]

Degree of study of the problem. The process of socialization is a process that occurs as a result of the interaction of an individual with society. The process of socialization is one of the most important subjects of the social sphere. In particular, the factor of socialization of the disabled is a separate field of research.

The process of a person entering the social environment, adapting to it, mastering certain roles and functions occurs at different levels: physiological, psychological, cognitive, professional, social-communicative. At the same time, the adaptation mechanism of socialization works throughout a person's life, which allows him to adapt to changes in the surrounding social environment. The features of this environment, the laws in force in it, norms and rules of interpersonal communication, traditions and new trends in social development have a decisive influence on the vectors of the individual's socialization process. No less important is the system of social communications, intercultural and interethnic relations in the society surrounding the individual.

It should be noted that when studying the influence of various factors on the socialization of an individual, the role of reading as a special system of interpersonal relationships between the reader and the author of the text being read in this process has not been studied deeply enough. [4] At the same time, the change of text carriers occurring in the digital era, changing not only the perception of the text, but also the traditional relationship between the author and the reader, and studying the impact of reading on the socialization process. Modern society and its communicative environment

are characterized by a number of fundamentally new social practices and technologies of social interaction, defined by theorists as an information society. Under the influence of global digitalization, a world of new forms, styles and meanings of social existence is being created, with new value priorities, a new architecture of interpersonal and social relations. A new style of social behavior is being formed, which can be defined as “information and communication,” and new forms of social connections are emerging network communities. Thanks to this, a person has the opportunity for close contacts and self-realization not only in the surrounding society, but also on a global scale. Social existence is filled with new discourse and motivations. At the same time, knowledge and information for many members of modern society becomes the highest value, and the degree of ownership they are a determining factor of social differentiation [5].

However, the network space, according to a number of social philosophers (G. Martin, Z. Sardar, H. Schumann, U. Eco, V. Inozemtsev, N. N. Moiseev and others), is fraught with certain dangers. Many scientists, including anthropologists, neurophysiologists, and psychologists, are seriously concerned about the ongoing changes in human mental and social activity in the modern virtual world. It has been proven that, by accelerating the processes of production and transmission of information, electronic technologies “wash out” slow, thoughtful thinking and the development of personal knowledge from a person’s cognitive space. Thus, the ability for analytical and logical thinking and reflection is reduced, and the so-called flickering consciousness is formed.

In addition, in the conditions of widespread digitalization, a person, finding himself in a world filled with various information, and not having the skills to process and assimilate it, prefers short texts with simple content, equipped with images that help understand its meaning. It is also significant that the phenomenon of “real virtually” often changes the objective reflection and vision of the world [6]. In this regard, I would like to recall the famous saying of the 17th century English philosopher George Berkeley: “To be is to be perceived.” It was understood as a metaphysical conclusion, but today it has actually become a real practice of the cyber environment: that is, if you are not in it, then you do not exist.

At the same time, the possibility of modifying the perceived world at one’s discretion, offered by the electronic environment, blurs the boundaries between real existence and the virtual model. Technologies make it easy to supplement reality, retouch it, throw out fragments from it that someone doesn’t like, and add new, more desirable ones. And questions involuntarily arise: firstly, what should be the ethical standards and guidelines in a society that observes the world through a virtual window, where there is a retouched picture that is inadequate to the real world; and secondly, will a person be able to resist the manipulation of his consciousness in the media environment?

The negative impact of the above factors on the process of socialization of the individual in the modern digital world can be reduced by using various tools, channels and methods for developing critical thinking, cognitive and social-communicative abilities of a person.

Cultural competence serves as the main condition of socialization of a person and at the same time as its result.

The components of a person's cultural competence consist of the following characteristics:

- to know the ideological and cultural foundations, values and traditions of the relevant society in its historical development;
- knowledge of laws, norms, rules, traditions, symbols adopted in a particular society;
- the ability to acquire a certain amount of ordinary and special (professional) knowledge, skills and qualifications, use them and interpret them in different ways;
- mastering verbal and non-verbal channels of social communication [7].

In a digital society, an important component of an individual’s cultural competence is also his mastery of modern network technologies, including the media environment, and the ability to use them effectively in everyday life and professional activities.

The level of cultural competence of an individual has a decisive influence on his ability to evaluate the information received and, if necessary, resist the manipulating influence on his consciousness and behavior of negative factors of the mass media, which often use unacceptable methods of disinformation and falsification in covering individual events and facts. Only a person

with a sufficiently high level of cultural competence is able to distinguish genuine knowledge from “counter-knowledge,” that is, false, unreliable knowledge and fake messages, and not become an object of social manipulation.

The above components of cultural competence have their own characteristics for each individual and are formed under the influence of a number of factors. We can distinguish the following levels: macro factors - political, socio-economic and cultural life of the country, moral values and ideals of society as a whole; mesofactors – place of residence, its regional characteristics, rules and traditions of the surrounding society, ethnic and religious affiliation; micro factors - family upbringing, school and university education, the nature and conditions of work, subcultural environment.

At each level, reading is an effective tool for developing an individual’s cultural competence, since basic civilizational values and their semantic models are codified and transmitted in society to a large extent through such phenomena as text and books.

Discussion. We define reading as a form of communicative, educational, cognitive and emotionally developing activity of the individual, and text as a space of communication between the author and the reader. It does not matter what material medium the text is in – printed, handwritten, electronic or online. The attitude towards text information in the reading process is influenced by ideological, social, cognitive, psychological, and physiological factors [8]. The personal, deep, creative nature of the reading process, which has its own logic and characteristics, is also obvious. It can be seen that reading is an important factor in the socialization of a person. Reading and libraries are considered a necessary factor in their socialization due to limited access to information, especially for visually impaired people. This is especially important for visually impaired people. Special libraries are important for visually impaired people to have access to books and other press publications due to the fact that publications in special writing for people with visual impairments are published in a small number of copies and each user has limited access to it personally.

The availability of convenient opportunities for obtaining information is an important factor in the process of socialization of persons with disabilities, as well as of all people. In this sense, libraries designed for people with visual disabilities serve to ensure their socialization through access to information. Because in Article 2 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by the UN on December 12, 2006 and ratified by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 695 of June 7, 2021. ““Communication” includes languages, display of text, Braille, tactile communication, large print, accessible multimedia as well as written, audio, plain-language, human-reader and augmentative and alternative modes, means and formats of communication, including accessible information and communication technology;” [9] - recognized as.

In Uzbekistan, the needs of people with visual disabilities were initially met on the basis of the Louis Braille book collection of the state library named after Alisher Navoi - now the National Library of Uzbekistan. Later, a system of separate libraries for users with visual disabilities was established in Uzbekistan, taking into account its specific aspects. This system has a history of its establishment. The first library serving people with visual disabilities in Uzbekistan was established in 1951 on the basis of the order No. 146 of September 12, 1951 of the former executive committee of the Tashkent region. The library performed its activities as a library for the blind in Tashkent city. The Louis Braille book fund of the library was originally formed on the basis of the publications of the state library named after Alisher Navoi and the club owned by the Blind Society of Uzbekistan. The funds of the first special library were used by persons with visual disabilities living in the capital. At the same time, in 1949, the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan established a printing house producing literature in L. Braille. His first product was the textbook "Alifbe", published on September 1, 1949 in L. Braille. The activity of this enterprise later became important in enriching the library's book collection with Uzbek language works written in L. Braille alphabet.

In the following period, the need to provide services to people with visual disabilities living in the provinces of the republic through special libraries also increased. Taking this into account, on the initiative of the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan, the Tashkent city library for the blind was transformed into the Republican Central Library for the Blind under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic. On January 1, 1966, the Republican Central Library for the Blind began its activity on the

basis of the Tashkent city library for the blind. Since then, this institution has been a methodical and coordinating center for providing library services for people with visual disabilities in the republic. Also, in the universal scientific libraries of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the regions, separate departments were established that collect books published in L. Braille. Thus, provision of library services for visually impaired persons was established. This opportunity became important in the use of press publications by people with visual disabilities through the library at that time.

On May 14, 1971, taking into account the proposals of the Ministry of Culture and the Ministry of Social Welfare, a special government decision "On special libraries for the blind" was adopted to improve services to the population.

This decision stipulates the following:

1. On the basis of L. Braille book section of the regional universal scientific libraries, to establish special libraries for the blind in cities and district centers where there are many people with visual disabilities.

Applying the norms established in the plan of public libraries in the organization of special libraries.

2. The Ministry of Culture of the Republic, in agreement with the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Social Security, will develop the charter of special libraries for the blind.

3. The Ministry of Culture was tasked with approving the model project of special libraries for the blind as proposed.

The decision to allocate one librarian to 250 blind users;

Allocation of bibliobus driver for the library.

On the basis of the above decision, by 1973 libraries for the blind were established in eleven regions of Uzbekistan. In 1970, under the publishing house of the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan, a publishing department of audio-recorded books was established. This activity was carried out on the basis of a list of literature compiled taking into account the interests of users. Importantly, all publications published before 1990 were sent free of charge to special blind libraries in the republic at the expense of the funds of the Society of the Blind of Uzbekistan. In 1975, in order to widely promote scientific and natural knowledge, the audio magazine "Mash'al" was published in cooperation with the Central Libraries of the Republic and the "Bir Safda" magazine of the Central Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This activity, prepared on the basis of articles in periodical press publications of our republic, continued until 1985. Library branches, mobile libraries and audio libraries were organized in sanatoriums and enterprises related to the society in order to create convenience for blind users who live far away from the Republican Central Library, library branch and mobile libraries owned by the Blind Society of Uzbekistan.

Results. After the independence of Uzbekistan, this activity continued at a new level. After the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 20, 2006 "On organization of provision of information-library to the population of the Republic", libraries for the blind were placed under the control of the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs. Based on this decision, in 2007 Jizzakh city library for the blind, in 2008 Karmana city library for the blind, Sirdarya city library for the blind were transformed into regional libraries for the blind in these regions. In 2008, a library for the blind of the Tashkent region was established in Kibray district.

Even today, a number of legal mechanisms are used in Uzbekistan in order to increase the level of socialization of persons with visual disabilities by obtaining information and using special library services. For example, in Article 26 of the Law on "Rights of Persons with Disabilities" adopted on July 22, 2020 "The state guarantees the realization of the rights of persons with disabilities to receive information and provides persons with disabilities with information intended for the general public, in convenient formats and using technologies that take into account different forms of disabilities... The state ensures the publication of fiction, school textbooks, other didactic materials and teaching tools using alternative forms of communication (Braille and voice forms) it is stated that [2].

Uzbekistan joined the "Treaty of Morocco" on facilitating the use of published works by persons with visual impairments and other disabilities in the perception of printed information. This

agreement was adopted in Morocco on June 27, 2013 and entered into force on September 30, 2016. "Treaty of Morocco" was ratified by the President's decision on January 12, 2022. The Agreement is part of the copyright system of the World Intellectual Property Organization.

There are three important principles of this agreement:

In the territory of the countries that have ratified the agreement, copyright is not required for the preparation, modification, publication and distribution of books and publications in a format intended for persons with visual disabilities;

Creating inclusive opportunities in mass publishing;

Mutual exchange of technologies related to the field between Azo countries.

According to the 2021 report of the Central Library of the Republic of the Blind

Today, more than 72 thousand blind people live in the republic. About 52,000 of them are readers. There are 138 libraries for the blind in the country.

Including: Republican libraries for the blind - 2.

Provincial libraries for the blind - 12.

City libraries for the blind - 11 cities

District libraries for the blind - 116

The total number of users of blind libraries in the republic is 88,055.

Including: 40,215 members of the Blind Society of Uzbekistan.

The total book fund of blind libraries in the republic is 620,817 units of account.

Including: Louis Braille publications - 136,409 units of account.

Audio books - 175,566 units of account.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that the libraries for the visually impaired in Uzbekistan satisfied their need for information and served as a necessary mechanism for their socialization. This creates a barrier-free environment in the field of information for people with visual impairments and creates a wide opportunity for them to work freely in various fields.

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ЎШБУ ЖУРНАЛ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ ТОМОНИДАН МОЛИЯЛАШТИРИЛГАН ИЛ-4821891548 “ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАҲДИД ВА ДАЪВАТЛАР ШАРОИТИДА ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ВА БЕЛАРУСЬ ЁШЛАРИ ОНГИ ШАКЛЛАНИШИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ-МАДАНИЙ ВА АКСИОЛОГИК АСОСЛАРИ” НОМЛИ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬ ЛОЙИҲА ДОИРАСИДА НАШРГА ТАЙЁРЛАНГАН.

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ДАННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ПОДГОТОВЛЕН К ИЗДАНИЮ В РАМКАХ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОГО НАУЧНОГО ПРОЕКТА ИЛ-4821891548 “СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ И АКСИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СОЗНАНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И БЕЛАРУСИ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УГРОЗ И ВЫЗОВОВ”

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